

Supplementary Data - Specialized Code

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1. Direct-repeats flanking ICE detection

Direct-repeats flanking ICE detection Documentation

The characteristic structure of direct repeats (DRs) flanking the ICEs help to demarcate the boundaries of the predicted ICEs(1, 2). Based on the identification of signature functional protein modules of ICE (encoding at least one integrase, a relaxase, a CP, and a VirB4), we use this semi-automated scripts and the contigs containing these modules as input to detect the Direct repeats structures upstream and downstream of the core modules, serving as markers for the identification and boundaries of ICEs/VICEs.

The Direct-repeats flanking ICE detection pipeline consists of the following steps:

- a) The bacterial genome of interest (contigs containing signature modules and over 5000 bp) is annotated using the PGAP annotation server in order to create an annotated GenBank file, which is then input into the script.
- b) The Biopython package is used to extract the location and annotated name of each CDS from the annotated GenBank file, and this information is then saved to a comma-separated value file.
- c) A set of predefined, user-adjustable ICE-associated CDS is used to scan the CSV file generated in the previous step. Any CDS with an annotation name that related to signature protein (e.g., "recombinase", "mobA", "relaxase ", etc.) is considered a 'hit', which was in accordance with previous identification of signature functional protein modules of ICE via HMM search.
- d) Distinguish between upstream and downstream of the tandem hit region. Then, apply a sliding window to iterate over the sequence data to help identify DR sequences. Compute proximity or length: For each DR sequence found, calculate its proximity to the hit region or its length. Determine the closest or longest DR sequence: Keep track of the DR sequence that is closest to or longest from the

hit region.

- e) Output the corresponding DR sequences, DR lengths, and the distances between DR and ICE hit region to a file, and generate a simple sketch of ICE structure information.

Source code-python script

```
## DR flanking ICE detection
```

```
## Python Scripts
```

```
from collections import defaultdict
```

```
import numpy as np
```

```
import os
```

```
from Bio import SeqIO
```

```
import shutil
```

```
import pandas as pd
```

```
from sklearn.cluster import MeanShift, estimate_bandwidth
```

```
from Bio.Graphics import GenomeDiagram
```

```
from Bio.SeqFeature import SeqFeature, FeatureLocation
```

```
from reportlab.lib import colors
```

```
import random
```

```
#parameters settings
```

```
with open('hit_protein_id.txt', 'r') as file:
```

```
hit_protein_id = file.read().strip()
```

```
hit_gene_strings = hit_protein_id.split("|")
```

```
sensitivity=0.3
```

```
Minimum_hits_needed_for_a_cluster=0
```

```
Num_flanking_genes=1
```

```
ex_delimiter = str("\t")
```

```
def input(input_file):
```

```
    global file_name, folder_name, gbk_file
```

```
    # input
```

```
    os.chdir(r'C:\Users\zilic\Desktop\phageminer')
```

```
    gbk_file = r"D:\DATA\ICE\ICE flanking\ICE_contig_gbk_dir\{}".format(input_file)
```

```
    #file_name = gbk_file.rsplit('.', 1)[0]
```

```
    #file_name = file_name.rsplit("\\", 1)[1]
```

```
    #file_name = file_name.replace(" ", "_")
```

```
    file_name = ICENO
```

```
    folder_name = r"C:\Users\zilic\Desktop\phageminer\ICE1207_pm\{}".format(file_name)
```

```
def create_working_folders():
```

```

global folder_name
if os.path.exists(folder_name):
    folder_name = "{}_plus_{}".format(folder_name,random.randint(500, 1000))
else:
    os.makedirs(folder_name)
if not os.path.exists("{}gbkformat".format(folder_name)):
    os.makedirs("{}gbkformat".format(folder_name))
if not os.path.exists("{}with_flanking".format(folder_name)):
    os.makedirs("{}with_flanking".format(folder_name))
if not os.path.exists("{}DR_delimit".format(folder_name)):
    os.makedirs("{}DR_delimit".format(folder_name))

def Prepare_all_CDS():
    global csv_file
    csv_file = "{}CDS_list.txt".format(folder_name)
    with open(csv_file, "w") as text_file:
        text_file.write(
            ("Minimum" + (ex_delimiter) + "Maximum" + (ex_delimiter) + "Sequence" +
            (ex_delimiter) + "Name" + (
                ex_delimiter) + "Locustag" + "\n"))

    for rec in SeqIO.parse(gbk_file, "genbank"):
        if rec.features:
            for feature in rec.features:
                if feature.type == "CDS":
                    with open(csv_file, "a") as text_file:
                        # Try using product names (ideal if genomes were annotated with Prokka).
                        Otherwise, use default CDS name
                        try:
                            text_file.write(
                                (str(feature.location.start) + (ex_delimiter) + str(feature.location.end) + (
                                    ex_delimiter) + str(feature.location.extract(rec).seq) + (ex_delimiter) +
                                str(
                                    feature.qualifiers["product"][0]) + (ex_delimiter) + str(
                                    feature.qualifiers["locus_tag"][0])) + "\n")
                        except KeyError as e:
                            if str(e) != "product":
                                text_file.write((str(feature.location.start + 1) + (ex_delimiter) + str(
                                    feature.location.end) + (ex_delimiter) +
                                str(feature.location.extract(rec).seq) + (
                                    ex_delimiter) + str(
                                    feature.qualifiers["product"][0]) + (ex_delimiter) + str(
                                    feature.qualifiers["locus_tag"][0])) + "\n")

```

```

def sig_hits_remove_pseudo_hits():
    global df_all, df, index_of_hits, df_list, df_sig_genes_extract
    ## define sig Protein hit
    # all contig region df_all
    df_all = pd.read_csv(csv_file, sep='\t')
    df_all["Minimum"] = df_all["Minimum"].astype(str).str.replace("<", "").str.replace(">", "")
    df_all["Maximum"] = df_all["Maximum"].astype(str).str.replace("<", "").str.replace(">", "")
    df_list = df_all.index.tolist()
    # hit gene region df
    df = df_all
    df.head()
    df = df[(df["Minimum"].astype(int) >= (int(ICE_region_dic[ICE][0][0])-1)) &
            (df["Maximum"].astype(int) <= (int(ICE_region_dic[ICE][0][1]+1))]

    ##Search for sig related genes in CDS list
    df_sig_genes_extract = df[df["Maximum"].astype(str).isin(hit_gene_locend)]
    df_sig_genes_extract.to_csv("{}sig_genes_hits.csv".format(folder_name))
    index_of_hits = df_sig_genes_extract.index.tolist()
    # Remove the following catches from the hits
    for key in index_of_hits:
        print(key)
        if any(x in df.loc[key, 'Name'] for x in ignore_gene):
            index_of_hits.remove(key)
    # For visual checks
    print("Hits for putative signature related genes in the genome: \n")
    for key in index_of_hits:
        print((key, df.loc[key, 'Name']))
    print("\n" * 5)

def capture_flanking_region():
    global dictionary_hits, flanking_regions_and_hits, hit_cord
    #dictionary_hits: dic{} for sig_hits location
    dictionary_hits = defaultdict(list)
    # Only consider clusters that have at least a certain number of hits
    if len(index_of_hits) > Minimum_hits_needed_for_a_cluster:
        for key in index_of_hits:
            dictionary_hits[ICE].append(key)

    # flanking_regions_and_hits: dic{} for sig_hits location with flanking around
    flanking_regions_and_hits = defaultdict(list)
    if len(index_of_hits) > Minimum_hits_needed_for_a_cluster:
        # setting up empty lists for calculations
        hit_cord = []
        # getting the minimum and maximum coordination of hits from dictionary_hits

```

```

for key in index_of_hits:
    hit_cord.append(key)
flanking_min_cord = min(hit_cord) - Num_flanking_genes
flanking_max_cord = max(hit_cord) + Num_flanking_genes
if flanking_min_cord < min(df_list):
    flanking_min_cord = min(df_list)
if flanking_max_cord > max(df_list):
    flanking_max_cord = max(df_list)
flanking_regions_and_hits[ICE].append(flanking_min_cord)
flanking_regions_and_hits[ICE].append(flanking_max_cord)

## export /with_flanking/all_CDS_withFlanking.txt
with open("{}_with_flanking/all_CDS_withFlanking.txt".format(folder_name), "w") as
text_file:
    text_file.write(("Cluster Number" + (ex_delimiter) + "Name" + (ex_delimiter) +
"Minimum" + (
    ex_delimiter) + "Maximum" + (ex_delimiter) + "Sequence" + "\n")))
    for key in df_list[flanking_min_cord:flanking_max_cord]:
        with open("{}_with_flanking/all_CDS_withFlanking.txt".format(folder_name), "a") as
text_file:
            text_file.write((str(1)) + ex_delimiter + (df_all.loc[key, 'Name']) + ex_delimiter + str(
                (df_all.loc[key, 'Minimum'])) + ex_delimiter + str((df_all.loc[key, 'Maximum'])) +
ex_delimiter + str(
                (df_all.loc[key, 'Sequence'])) + "\n")

def capture_flanking_into_gbk():
    for key in range(len(flanking_regions_and_hits)):
        for seq_record in SeqIO.parse(gbk_file, "genbank"):
            gbk_min_cord = int((df_all.loc[flanking_regions_and_hits[ICE][0], 'Minimum']))
            gbk_max_cord = int((df_all.loc[flanking_regions_and_hits[ICE][1], 'Maximum']))
            records = seq_record[gbk_min_cord:gbk_max_cord]
            records.description = 'Cluster_{}_{}'.format(key + 1, file_name)
            records.id = 'Cluster_{}'.format(key + 1)
            # Try to save file, but if you get an error that the Locus identifier is too long (could
            happen if genomes are annotated by Prokka), then shorten the locus identifier to 10 characters
            try:
                SeqIO.write(records, "{}_with_flanking/{}_withFlanking.gbk".format(folder_name,
file_name), "genbank")
            except ValueError as e:
                if str(e) != "Locus identifier %r is too long":
                    records.name = records.name[:10]
                    SeqIO.write(records,
                    "{}_with_flanking/{}_withFlanking.gbk".format(folder_name, filename), "genbank")

```

```

def find_duplicate_substrings(string1, string2, min_length, max_length):
    duplicate_substrings = []

    for length in range(min_length, max_length + 1):
        for i in range(len(string1) - length + 1):
            substring = string1[i:i+length]

            if substring in string2 and substring not in duplicate_substrings:
                duplicate_substrings.append(substring)

    return duplicate_substrings

def DR_detection():
    global DR_final
    for key in range(len(flanking_regions_and_hits)):
        for seq_record in SeqIO.parse(gbk_file, "genbank"):
            ICE_core_up_cord= int((df_all.loc[min(hit_cord), 'Minimum']))
            ICE_core_down_cord= int((df_all.loc[max(hit_cord), 'Maximum']))
            gbk_min_cord = int((df_all.loc[flanking_regions_and_hits[ICE][0], 'Minimum']))
            gbk_max_cord = int((df_all.loc[flanking_regions_and_hits[ICE][1], 'Maximum']))
            print("ICE plus putative flanking region is from",gbk_min_cord,"to",gbk_max_cord)
            print("ICE core region is from", ICE_core_up_cord, "to", ICE_core_down_cord)

            #Divide the upstream and downstream regions for DR detection.
            flanking_record_up = str(seq_record[gbk_min_cord:ICE_core_up_cord].seq)
            flanking_record_down = str(seq_record[ICE_core_down_cord:gbk_max_cord].seq)

            #detection DR
            DR_match =
            find_duplicate_substrings(flanking_record_up,flanking_record_down,6,20)

            if DR_match:
                ##Filter pricinple1:DR length in priority
                lengths = []
                for DR in DR_match:
                    lengths.append(len(DR))
                DR_longest = [DR for DR, length in zip(DR_match, lengths) if length >=
max(lengths)]

                ##Filter pricinple1:DR distance in priority
                distances = []
                for DR in DR_longest:
                    DR_upstream_loc = flanking_record_up.index(DR)
                    DR_downstream_loc = flanking_record_down.index(DR)

```

```

distance = len(flanking_record_up) - DR_upstream_loc + DR_downstream_loc
print("DR_upstream_loc is",DR_upstream_loc)
print("DR_downstream_loc is", DR_downstream_loc)
print("len(flanking_record_up) is", len(flanking_record_up))
print("Direct Repeats", DR, "was detected, the length is", len(DR))
print("DR distance is", distance)
print(distance)
position = defaultdict(list)
distances.append(distance)
DR_final = [DR for DR, distance in zip(DR_longest, distances) if distance <=
min(distances)]
print(DR_final)

DR_final_upstream = flanking_record_up.index(DR_final[0])
DR_final_downstream = flanking_record_down.index(DR_final[0])

## export ICE_delimit_DNA
ICE_delimit = flanking_record_up[DR_final_upstream:] + str(
    seq_record[ICE_core_up_cord:ICE_core_down_cord].seq) +
flanking_record_down[0:DR_final_downstream+len(DR_final[0])]
ICE_delimit_file =
"{} /DR_delimit/ICE_delimit_DNA_seq.fas".format(folder_name)
with open(ICE_delimit_file, "w") as file:
    file.write(">" + ICE + "\n" + ICE_delimit)

## export ICE_delimit_gbk
for seq_record in SeqIO.parse(gbk_file, "genbank"):
    start_DR = gbk_min_cord + DR_final_upstream
    end_DR = ICE_core_down_cord + DR_final_downstream + len(DR_final[0])
    print(start_DR,end_DR)
    records = seq_record[start_DR:end_DR]
    records.description = '{}_withDR'.format(file_name)
    records.id = 'Cluster_{}'.format(key + 1)
    # Try to save file, but if you get an error that the Locus identifier is too long
    (could happen if genomes are annotated by Prokka), then shorten the locus identifier to 10
    characters
    try:
        SeqIO.write(records, "{} /gbkformat/{}_ICEwithDR.gbk".format(folder_name,
file_name), "genbank")
    except ValueError as e:
        if str(e) != "Locus identifier %r is too long":
            records.name = records.name[:10]
            SeqIO.write(records,

```

```

"{} /gbkformat/flanking_{}_ICEwithDR.gbk".format(folder_name, file_name), "genbank")
    ## export DR info
    DR_file = "{} /DR_delimit/DR_info.txt".format(folder_name)
    with open(DR_file, "w") as text_file:
        text_file.write(
            ICE + (ex_delimiter) + str(DR_final[0]) + (ex_delimiter) +
str(len(DR_final[0])) + (
            ex_delimiter) + str(min(
                distances)) + (ex_delimiter) + str(start_DR) + (ex_delimiter) + str(end_DR))
    else:
        print("No Direct Repeats was detected")
        DR_file = "{} /DR_delimit/DR_info.txt".format(folder_name)
        with open(DR_file, "w") as text_file:
            text_file.write(
                ICE + (ex_delimiter) + "Notfound_DR" + (ex_delimiter) + "0" + (ex_delimiter)
+ "0" + (ex_delimiter) + "no_adjust" + (ex_delimiter) + "no_adjust")
            for seq_record in SeqIO.parse(gbk_file, "genbank"):
                ICE_core_up_cord = int((df_all.loc[min(hit_cord), 'Minimum']))
                ICE_core_down_cord = int((df_all.loc[max(hit_cord), 'Maximum']))
                records = seq_record[ICE_core_up_cord:ICE_core_down_cord]
                records.description = 'Cluster_{}_{}'.format(key + 1, file_name)
                records.id = 'Cluster_{}'.format(key + 1)
                SeqIO.write(records, "{} /gbkformat/{}_ICEwithoutDR.gbk".format(folder_name,
file_name), "genbank")

def save_into_pdf():
    # genebank file prepare
    with open("{} /with_flanking/upstream_downstream_CDS.txt".format(folder_name), "w")
as text_file:
        text_file.write(
            (("gbk_splited" + (ex_delimiter) + "Name" + (ex_delimiter) + "locustag" + (
                ex_delimiter) + "Sequence" + "\n")))
        for key in range(len(flanking_regions_and_hits)):
            for seq_record in SeqIO.parse(gbk_file, "genbank"):
                gbk_min_cord = int((df_all.loc[flanking_regions_and_hits[ICE][0], 'Minimum']))
                gbk_max_cord = int((df_all.loc[flanking_regions_and_hits[ICE][1], 'Maximum']))
                records = seq_record[gbk_min_cord:gbk_max_cord]
                records.description = 'Cluster_{}_{}'.format(key + 1, file_name)
                records.id = 'Cluster_{}'.format(key + 1)
                # Try to save file, but if you get an error that the Locus identifier is too long (could
happen if genomes are annotated by Prokka), then shorten the locus identifier to 10 characters
                try:
                    SeqIO.write(records,
"{} /gbkformat/{}_withFlanking.gbk".format(folder_name, file_name), "genbank")

```

```

except ValueError as e:
    if str(e) != "Locus identifier %r is too long":
        records.name = records.name[:10]
        SeqIO.write(records,
"{{/gbkformat/{{}_withFlanking.gbk".format(folder_name,file_name), "genbank")
        # GD diagram
        for key in range(len(flanking_regions_and_hits)):
            record =
SeqIO.read("{{/gbkformat/{{}_withFlanking.gbk".format(folder_name,file_name), "genbank")
            gd_diagram = GenomeDiagram.Diagram(record.id)
            gd_track_for_features = gd_diagram.new_track(2, name="Name")
            gd_feature_set = gd_track_for_features.new_set()
            for feature in record.features:
                if feature.type == "CDS":
                    # Define how the CDS should lool like in the figure
                    # Colour hits red and the rest blue
                    # Try to see if the "product" qualifer exists, if yes use that
                    try:
                        if any(key in feature.qualifiers["locus_tag"][0] for key in
df_sig_genes_extract["Locustag"]):
                            color = colors.red
                        elif any(key in feature.qualifiers["locus_tag"][0] for key in df["Locustag"]):
                            color = colors.blue
                    else:
                        color = colors.yellow
                    with
open("{{/with_flanking/upstream_downstream_CDS.txt".format(folder_name), "a") as
text_file:
                    text_file.write(
                        (str(ICE)) + ex_delimiter + (feature.qualifiers["product"][0]) +
ex_delimiter + str(
                            feature.qualifiers["locus_tag"][0]) + ex_delimiter + str(
                                feature.location.extract(record).seq) + "\n")

                # if it has no product name, and hence an error is encountered, then just go with the
default qualifier
            except KeyError:
                if any(key in feature.qualifiers for key in key in
df_sig_genes_extract["Locustag"]):
                    color = colors.red
                elif any(key in feature.qualifiers for key in key in df["Locustag"]):
                    color = colors.blue
                else:
                    color = colors.yellow

```

```

feature.qualifiers['locus_tag']=feature.qualifiers["product"]
gd_feature_set.add_feature(feature, sigil="ARROW",
                           color=color, label=True,
                           label_size=6, label_angle=45, label_position="middle", )

# Highlight assembly gaps in green
for site, name, color in [(("NNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNNN", "assembly gap",
colors.green)]:
    index = 0
    while True:
        index = record.seq.find(site, start=index)
        if index == -1: break
        feature = SeqFeature(FeatureLocation(index, index + len(site)))
        gd_feature_set.add_feature(feature, color=color, name=name,
                                   label= True, label_size=10,
                                   label_color=color, label_position="middle", )
        index += len(site)

# Highlight assembly gaps in purple
for site, name, color in [(DR_final[0], "DR", colors.purple)]:
    index = 0
    while True:
        index = record.seq.find(site, start=index)
        if index == -1: break
        feature = SeqFeature(FeatureLocation(index , index + len(site)))
        gd_feature_set.add_feature(feature, color=color, name=name,
                                   label=True, label_size=10,
                                   label_color=color, label_position="middle", )
        index += len(site)

gd_diagram.draw(format="linear", pagesize=(10 * 72, 10 * 72), orientation='landscape',
fragment_size=1,
                fragments=1,
                start=0, tracklines=0, track_size=0.2, x=0.05, y=0.35, end=len(record))
gd_diagram.write("{}\visualization.pdf".format(folder_name), "PDF")

def run_workflow(input_file):
    input(input_file)
    create_working_folders()
    Prepare_all_CDS()
    sig_hits_remove_pseudo_hits()
    capture_flanking_region()
    DR_detection()

```

```

capture_flanking_into_gbk()
save_into_pdf()

#####
## RUN
with open(r"D:\DATA\Data-Bridge\sig_gene_loc_end.txt", 'r') as file:
    hit_gene_locend_strings = file.read()
    hit_gene_locend_strings = hit_gene_locend_strings.replace("\n", "")
    hit_gene_locend = hit_gene_locend_strings.split("|")

data = pd.read_csv("D:\DATA\Data-Bridge\ICE_info.csv")
data.head()
#print(data['ice_start_end'])
#print(data['ICENAME'])
#print(data['gbk_splitid'])
ICE_region_dic= defaultdict(list)
ICE_file_dic = defaultdict(list)
for ICE in data['ICENAME']:
    str_loc = data.loc[data['ICENAME'] == ICE, 'ice_start_end'].values.tolist()
    start = int(str_loc[0].split("..")[0])
    end= int(str_loc[0].split("..")[1])
    start_end = (start,end)
    ICE_region_dic[ICE].append(start_end)
    str_file = data.loc[data['ICENAME'] == ICE, 'gbk_splitid'].values.tolist()
    ICE_file_dic[ICE].append(str_file)

for ICE in data['ICENAME']:
    file = ICE_file_dic[ICE]
    gbkfile = "{}.gbk".format(file[0][0])
    ICENO = data.loc[data['ICENAME'] == ICE, 'NO'].values.tolist()[0]
    print(gbkfile)
    run_workflow(gbkfile)

```

2. ICE Activity Scores Calculator

ICE Activity Scores Calculator Documentation

The ICE Activity Scores Calculator in this study is an R-script pipeline designed to evaluate structural similarity and infer ICE (Integrative and Conjugative Element) transfer-activity scores across species based on ICE-encoding protein orthogroups. The pipeline consists of the following key steps:

- 1) Initially, the orthogroup content matrix was generated using the OrthoFinder tool(3) , which uses the entire database of Mollicute ICE CDS as the analytical input. The similarity between each pair of ICEs was subsequently calculated.
- 2) To account for potential size loss during ICE transfer, this step used the Jaccard coefficient, as shown in equation (b). Coefficients exceeding the preliminary threshold of 0.2 were considered and included in the subsequent analysis. The ICE collection was then divided into different subsets (C1, C2, C3, ...Ck) on the basis of their host species.
- 3) A specific transfer scenario involving ICE_x and a target species was represented as the subset of Jaccard similarity between ICE_x and C_i (ICE collection in the target species), as shown in equation (c).
- 4) The final ICE transfer-activity score across species was determined by summing the Jaccard similarity considering all species groups, as shown in equation (d).

The method for inferring the transfer-activity score:

The method for inferring the transfer-activity score:

$$J(\text{ICE}_x, \text{ICE}_y) = |A \cap B| / |A \Delta B| \text{ (a)}$$

(A, B are the sets of Ortho groups for ICE_x and ICE_y, respectively.)

$$\text{Split}(\text{ICE database, hosts_species}) = \{C_1, C_2, C_3, \dots, C_k\} \text{ (b)}$$

$$J(\text{ICE}_x, C_i) = \{ J(\text{ICE}_x, \text{ICE}_y | \text{ICE}_y \in C_i) \} \text{ (c)}$$

$$\text{Predicted Active Score for ICE}_x = \sum_{i=1}^k \max(J(\text{ICE}_x, C_i)) \text{ (d)}$$

5) Visualization: The ICE similarity network and related information were visualized using Cytoscape, which provides a graphical representation of the relationships between ICEs. The related hierarchical clustering tree for ICEs/VICEs was generated by calculating pairwise distances between ICE entities on the basis of orthologous similarity measures. Several R packages were employed to streamline this process: cluster for implementing the hierarchical clustering algorithm(4), factoextra for assessing clustering efficacy(5), and ggtree for visualizing the resulting dendrogram(6).

Source code-R script

ICE Activity Scores Calculator

R Scripts

##Required packages

```
library(factoextra)
```

```
library(tidyr)
```

Active ICE network

```
jaccard_similarity <- function(A, B) {  
  intersection = length(intersect(A, B))  
  union = length(A) + length(B) - intersection  
  return (intersection/union)  
}
```

Jaccard similarity coefficient and function construction test.

```
jaccard_similarity(c(0,1,0,1),c(1,1,0,1))  
A=c(0,1,0,1)  
B=c(1,1,0,1)  
length(intersect(A, B))
```

Calculate ICE similarity

```
## JACCARD distance
```

```
## ICE-299-gccontent
```

```
library(factoextra)
```

```
tb1<-read.csv(file =
```

```
"D://DATA/ICE/orthofinder/0425_ICE_all_refer/Orthogroups/Orthogroups.GeneCount.tsv",sep = "\t")
```

```
tb2<-read.csv(file =
```

```
"D://DATA/ICE/orthofinder/0425_ICE_all_refer//Orthogroups/Orthogroups_UnassignedGene s.tsv",sep = "\t")
```

```
tb1[tb1>=1]=1 ## Transfer >1 value
```

```

tb2[!is.na(tb2) & tb2 !=""]=1
tb2[is.na(tb2)| tb2 =="" ]=0
tb_merge<- rbind(tb1[,-length(tb1)],tb2)
head(tb_merge)
tb_merge_t<-t(tb_merge)
colnames(tb_merge_t)<- paste0("OG",1:dim(tb_merge_t)[2])
tb_merge_t<-tb_merge_t[-1,]
head(gc_matrix)

## Annotation file 'anno'
## index_x is used to match orthofinder label
df <- ice_meta
colnames(df)
df$gbk_splitid
df$number_id
head(df)
df$index_x =paste(df$gbk_splitid,df$number_id,sep = "_Protein_")
df$index_x= str_replace_all(df$index_x,"-",".")
## Orthofinder file names do not allow '.', it will be automatically replaced with '.', so please
keep it consistent
rownames(gc_matrix)
df$index_x[is.na(df$gbk_splitid)]=df$NO[is.na(df$gbk_splitid)]
ice_meta$label=df$index_x
gc_matrix<-as.matrix(tb_merge_t) #####Row:ICE; Column:OG
dim(gc_matrix)

##Construct sim_df ICE similarity matrix 299x299
sim_df <- matrix(nrow = length(df$index_x),ncol = length(df$index_x),
                dimnames = list(c(df$index_x),c(df$index_x)))

## calculating
for (i in df$index_x){
  print(i)
  i_OG_group=names(which(gc_matrix[i,]=="1"))
  for (j in df$index_x) {
    j_OG_group=names(which(gc_matrix[j,]=="1"))
    sim_df[i,j]=jaccard_similarity(i_OG_group,j_OG_group)
  }
}

## Based on sim-df, convert the self-similarity values of 1 to 0 to obtain sim-durep,
facilitating the removal of self-similarity in subsequent steps.
head(sim_df)
sim_dframe <- as.data.frame(sim_df)

```

```

library(tidyr)
sim_dframe_durep <- sim_dframe
sim_dframe_durep <- matrix(data = 0,nrow = 299,ncol = 299,dimnames =
list(colnames(sim_dframe),rownames(sim_dframe)))
# deduplication
for (c in 1:dim(sim_dframe)[2]) {
  durep = c(c:299)
  print(durep)
  sim_dframe_durep[durep,c] <- sim_dframe[durep ,c]
}
sim_dframe_durep<-as.data.frame(sim_dframe_durep)

####Active score calculation
dim(sim_dframe_durep)
# anno
colnames(df)
df$gbk_splitid
df$number_id
head(df)

dim(sim_dframe_durep)
sim_dframe_durep<-as.data.frame(sim_dframe_durep)
### Similarity sim df converts to long data for easy network diagram drawing
cal_active_socre_df=gather(sim_dframe_durep,ICEindex1,similarity)
### Note that sim_dframe_durep is repeatedly set to 0, requiring subsequent filtering
cal_active_socre_df[is.na(cal_active_socre_df)]=0
cal_active_socre_df$ICEindex2<- rep(colnames(sim_df),299)
cal_active_socre_df<-
cal_active_socre_df[cal_active_socre_df$ICEindex1!=cal_active_socre_df$ICEindex2,]

cal_active_socre_df$source_specie =
df$taxonkit_specie[match(cal_active_socre_df$ICEindex1,df$index_x)]
cal_active_socre_df$end_specie =
df$taxonkit_specie[match(cal_active_socre_df$ICEindex2,df$index_x)]
cal_active_socre_df$source_NO =
df$NO[match(cal_active_socre_df$ICEindex1,df$index_x)]
cal_active_socre_df$end_NO = df$NO[match(cal_active_socre_df$ICEindex2,df$index_x)]
cal_active_socre_df$edge_type=ifelse(
  cal_active_socre_df$source_specie==cal_active_socre_df$end_specie,
  "same_specie","cross_specie"
)

# A threshold setting greater than 0 removes completely unrelated connections
threshold_similarity<-0.1

```

```

cal_active_socre_df_threshold <-
cal_active_socre_df[cal_active_socre_df$similarity>threshold_similarity,]
unique(cal_active_socre_df$source_NO[cal_active_socre_df$similarity>0.5 &
cal_active_socre_df$edge_type=="cross_specie"])#24
active_socre_each_specie <-
data.frame(end_specie=unique(cal_active_socre_df$end_specie))

### Take the maximum similarity between ICE and each species
data=cal_active_socre_df_threshold
for (ice in c(unique(cal_active_socre_df$source_NO))) {
  print(ice)
  ice_specie=data$source_specie[data$source_NO==ice][1]
  ice_df = data[data$source_NO==ice & data$end_specie!=ice_specie,]
  ice_score=ice_df %>% group_by(end_specie) %>% summarise(score=max(similarity,na.rm
= TRUE))
  active_socre_each_specie=left_join(active_socre_each_specie,ice_score,by="end_specie")
  colnames(active_socre_each_specie)=c(colnames(active_socre_each_specie)[-
length(colnames(active_socre_each_specie))],ice)
}
active_socre_each_specie[is.na(active_socre_each_specie)]=0

degree_count <- function(score){
  degree_count=sum(score>threshold_similarity)
  related_specie=active_socre_each_specie$end_specie[score>threshold_similarity]
  related_specie_vector=paste(related_specie,collapse = "|")
  degree_count_retrun=c(degree_count,related_specie_vector)
  return(degree_count_retrun)
}

## Take the sum of ICE and the maximum similarity of each species
active_score_each_ICE<-data.frame(ICE=colnames(active_socre_each_specie)[-1],

ICE_host=ice_meta$taxonkit_specie[match(colnames(active_socre_each_specie)[-
1],ice_meta$NO)],
  active_score=apply(active_socre_each_specie[,-1],2,sum)
  active_degree=apply(active_socre_each_specie[,-1],2,degree_count)[1,],
  related_specie=apply(active_socre_each_specie[,-1],2,degree_count)[2,])

df$active_score<-
active_score_each_ICE$active_score[match(df$NO,active_score_each_ICE$ICE)]

```

3. Mollicute chromosomal transfer (MCT) analysis

Mollicute chromosomal transfer (MCT) analysis Documentation

Based on the identification of horizontal gene transfer (HGT) across 26 species, this study employed the mean-shift clustering method to focus on regions with frequent HGT events. These regions, referred to as candidate Mollicute chromosomal transfer (MCT) zones, were identified using the *meanShiftR* package(7) by defining regions containing more than 10 tandem HGT genes as potential MCT cases. To differentiate MCT cases from integrative and conjugative elements (ICEs) within the same genome, we utilized the characteristic structure of direct repeats (DRs) flanking the ICE regions to define their boundaries. To manually validate and interpret the spatial relationship between ICE regions and MCT cases, colocalizations were visualized using the *gggenes* package.

The Mollicute chromosomal transfer (MCT) analysis pipeline in this study consists of the following steps:

- 1) Required Data: Predicted HGT gene information (genome data, HGT gene locations), which can be obtained from the HGTector tool and filtered through kernel density estimation.
- 2) Mean-Shift Scan for MCT Regions: Using the mean-shift clustering method in the *meanShiftR* package, the locations of the remaining HGT hits relative to each other and to the size of the host genome were used to identify clusters of HGT-related genes. During this step, minimal manual input from the user is required to ensure correct identification of MCT regions (in this study, the MCT criteria were set to at least 10 tandem HGT genes). If necessary, clustering can be repeated with different sensitivity settings as redefined by the user. If no clusters of HGT-related genes are detected, the pipeline is aborted at this stage.
- 3) Viewing the Location Relationship Between MCT and ICE Using *gggenes*: To differentiate MCT cases from ICEs within the same genome, we utilized the characteristic structure of DRs flanking the ICE regions to define their boundaries.
- 4) Correlation Analysis of ICE and Mollicute Chromosomal Transfer: Genome data were grouped based on ICE detection status (ICE detected, only vICE detected, neither ICE nor vICE detected), and the percentage of MCT detection in each group was calculated. The percentage of genomes with detected MCT events in each group was subsequently compared via Fisher's exact test. Bonferroni correction was applied to adjust for multiple testing.
- 5) Tracing MCT Events Back to Their Origins Using a Chord Diagram: The potential origin of these MCT cases was traced back using BLAST against a database of Mollicute genomes, with the following criteria: identity percentage ($\geq 70\%$),

alignment length (≥ 5000), coverage ($\geq 60\%$), and E-value ($\leq 1 \times 10^{-8}$).

Source code-R script

```
## Mollicute chromosomal transfer (MCT) analysis
```

```
## R Script
```

```
## Required packages
```

```
library(LPCM)
```

```
library(scales)
```

```
library(circlize)
```

```
library(reshape2)
```

```
library(gggenes)
```

```
library(ggplot2)
```

```
library(ggplot2)
```

```
library(RColorBrewer)
```

```
## MCT analysis
```

```
### MCT criteria: tandem HGT gene > 10
```

```
mct_phrase <- data.frame()
```

```
ncbi_hgts_meta_x = ncbi_hgts_meta[grepl("_", ncbi_hgts_meta[, "protein_id"]),]
```

```
## meanshift scan MCT region
```

```
library(LPCM)
```

```
cds_df <- as.data.frame(table(ncbi_cds_meta$contig))
```

```
colnames(cds_df) <- c("contig", "cds_num")
```

```
for (contig in unique(ncbi_hgts_meta_x$contig)) {
```

```
  hgt_contig <- ncbi_hgts_meta_x[ncbi_hgts_meta_x$contig == contig,]
```

```
  count <- str_count(hgt_contig[, "protein_id"], "_")[1]
```

```
  protein_sequence <- str_split_i(hgt_contig[, "protein_id"], "_", count + 1)
```

```
  sorted_vector <- as.numeric(protein_sequence)
```

```
  if (length(sorted_vector) >= 5) {
```

```
    contig_cds_num = cds_df[cds_df == contig, 2]
```

```
    sorted_vector = c(sorted_vector, contig_cds_num)
```

```
    ms_res = ms(sorted_vector, h = 0.01, thr = 0.1, scaled = 1)
```

```
    hgt_contig$mshift = ms_res[[2]][1:c(length(sorted_vector)-1)]
```

```
    ms_df <- table(ms_res[[2]][1:c(length(sorted_vector)-1)])
```

```
    hgt_no <- names(ms_df)[ms_df >= 10]
```

```
    mct_phrase_i = hgt_contig[hgt_contig$mshift %in% hgt_no,]
```

```
    mct_phrase = rbind(mct_phrase, mct_phrase_i)
```

```
  }
```

```
}
```

```
mct_phrase$mct_label = paste(mct_phrase$contig, mct_phrase$mshift, sep = "_")
```

```
mct_size <- table(mct_phrase$mct_label) %>% as.data.frame()
```

```
colnames(mct_size) <- c("mct_label", "mct_cds_num")
```

```

mct_phrase$mct_size <-
mct_size$mct_cds_num[match(mct_phrase$mct_label,mct_size$mct_label)]
mct_phrase$assembly<-
ncbi_hgts_meta$assembly[match(mct_phrase$contig,ncbi_hgts_meta$contig)]
mct_phrase$ice_relatd <- ifelse(mct_phrase$assembly %in%
unique(ice_meta$assembly_id),"yes","no" )
colnames(mct_phrase)
unique(mct_phrase$specie.x)

```

gggenes View the location relationship between MCT and ICE

step 1 contigs

```

MCT_ICE_contig <-
intersect(unique(ice_collect$contig_sim),unique(mct_phrase$contig_sim))
MCT_ICE_contig <- intersect(unique(ice_meta$contig_sim),unique(mct_phrase$contig_sim))
ice_meta$contig_sim<- str_remove(ice_meta$contig,"\\.[0-9]")
select_ICE <- ice_meta[ice_meta$contig_sim %in% MCT_ICE_contig,]
unique(select_ICE$contig_sim) #19 contigs
unique(select_ICE$assembly_id) #17 assemblys
unique(select_ICE$NO) #36 ICEs

```

step2 Determine the ICE starting position

```

select_ICE_location <- ice_meta[ice_meta$NO %in%
select_ICE$NO,c("NO","contig","start_adj","end_adj")]
select_ICE_location$start <- as.numeric(select_ICE_location$start_adj)
select_ICE_location$end<- as.numeric(select_ICE_location$end_adj)
select_ICE_location$strand<-"forward"
select_ICE_location$gene <- select_ICE_location$NO
select_ICE_location$protein <- select_ICE_location$NO
select_ICE_location$contig_sim<- str_remove(select_ICE_location$contig,"\\.[0-9]")

```

step3 Determine the location of the MCT region

step3.1 Determine the location of contig HGT gene where ICE is located

```

select_ICE_mct <- mct_phrase[mct_phrase$contig_sim %in% select_ICE$contig_sim,]
select_ICE_mct$strand <-
ifelse(grepl("complement",select_ICE_mct$location),"forward","reverse")
select_ICE_mct$location_sim <- gsub("complement\\(|\\)", "",select_ICE_mct$location)
select_ICE_mct$location_sim<- gsub("<|>", "",select_ICE_mct$location_sim)
select_ICE_mct$start <- as.numeric(str_split_i(select_ICE_mct$location_sim,"\\.",1))
select_ICE_mct$end <- as.numeric(str_split_i(select_ICE_mct$location_sim,"\\.",2))

```

```

mct_s_e<-data.frame(mct_label=unique(select_ICE_mct$mct_label),start=0,end=0)
for (mct in unique(select_ICE_mct$mct_label)) {
  mct_contig<-select_ICE_mct[select_ICE_mct$mct_label==mct,]
  mct_start_i=min(mct_contig[, "start"])

```

```

mct_end_i=max(mct_contig[,"end"])
mct_s_e[mct_s_e$mct_label==mct,"start"]=mct_start_i
mct_s_e[mct_s_e$mct_label==mct,c("end")]=mct_end_i
}
mct_s_e$contig_sim <-
mct_phrase$contig_sim[match(mct_s_e$mct_label,mct_phrase$mct_label)]
mct_s_e$strand <- c("forward")
mct_s_e$protein <- mct_s_e$mct_label
mct_s_e$gene <- mct_s_e$mct_label
unique(mct_s_e$mct_label)
unique(mct_s_e$contig_sim)
unique(select_ICE$NO)

## construct df for plot
df <- rbind(select_ICE_location[,c("contig_sim","gene","protein","start","end","strand")],
           mct_s_e[,c("contig_sim","gene","protein","start","end","strand")])

## Filter contigs based on ICE DR and integrity
df$type=ifelse(df$gene %in% mct_s_e$gene,"MCT_region","ICE_region")
df$DR=ice_meta$DR[match(df$contig_sim,ice_meta$contig_sim)]
contigs_DR=unique(df$contig_sim[df$DR=="DR_detected"])
contigs_complete <-
unique(ice_meta$contig_sim[ice_meta$genome_level=="Complete"|ice_meta$genome_level
==" Chromosome"])
select_contigs=intersect(contigs_DR,contigs_complete)
select_contigs=intersect(contigs_DR,unique(select_ICE$contig_sim))
ggplot(df[df$contig_sim %in% select_contigs,], aes(xmin = start, xmax = end, y = contig_sim,
fill = type)) +
  geom_gene_arrow(alpha=1) +facet_wrap(~ contig_sim, scales = "free_y", ncol = 1)+
  theme_genes()
ggplot(df[df$contig_sim %in% select_contigs,], aes(xmin = start, xmax = end, y = contig_sim,
fill = type)) +
  geom_gene_arrow(size=0.2,alpha=1,arrowhead_height = grid::unit(5,"mm")) +facet_wrap(~
contig_sim, scales = "free", ncol = 1)+
  theme_genes()+scale_fill_manual(values = c("ICE_region"
="#8FC9E2","MCT_region"="#ECC97F"))+
  labs(y="Assembly NO",fill="Type")+theme(text = element_text(size=10))

```

mct length distribution

```

colnames(mct_length)
mct_phrase$strand <- ifelse(grepl("complement",mct_phrase$location),"forward","reverse")
mct_phrase$location_sim <- gsub("complement\\(|\\)", "",mct_phrase$location)
mct_phrase$location_sim <- gsub("<|>", "",mct_phrase$location_sim)
mct_phrase$start <- as.numeric(str_split_i(mct_phrase$location_sim,"\\. ",1))

```

```

mct_phrase$end <- as.numeric(str_split_i(mct_phrase$location_sim,"\\.\"",2))

mct_length<-data.frame(mct_label=unique(mct_phrase$mct_label),start=0,end=0,specie=0)
for (mct in unique(mct_phrase$mct_label)) {
  mct_contig<- mct_phrase[mct_phrase$mct_label==mct,]
  mct_start_i=min(mct_contig[, "start"])
  mct_end_i=max(mct_contig[, "end"])
  mct_speie_i=unique(mct_contig[, "specie.x"])
  mct_length[mct_length$mct_label==mct, "start"]=mct_start_i
  mct_length[mct_length$mct_label==mct, c("end")]=mct_end_i
  mct_length[mct_length$mct_label==mct, c("specie")]=mct_speie_i
}
mct_length$length= mct_length$end - mct_length$start
ggplot(mct_length,aes(length))+geom_density()+facet_wrap(.~specie)
ggplot(mct_length,aes(length))+ geom_histogram(stat = "bin",binwidth =
2000,aes(fill=specie))+theme_bw()+
  scale_fill_manual(values = c(brewer.pal(11,"Paired")))+facet_wrap(.~specie,scales =
"free_y")+scale_x_continuous(limits = c(0,150000))+
  theme(text = element_text(size=10))+labs(x="MCT length",y="Count",fill="Specie")
mct_length$specie=str_replace(mct_length$specie,"_", " ")
ggplot(mct_length,aes(length))+ geom_histogram(stat = "bin",binwidth =
2000,color="grey",aes(fill=specie))+theme_bw()+
  scale_fill_manual(values = c(brewer.pal(11,"Paired")))+scale_x_continuous(limits =
c(0,150000),expand = c(0,0))+
  scale_y_continuous(expand = c(0,0.1))+
  theme(text = element_text(size=10))+labs(x="MCT length",y="Count",fill="Specie")
mct_length$Sice_related=
mct_phrase$Sice_relatd[match(mct_length$mct_label,mct_phrase$mct_label)]
table(mct_length$Sice_related)
ggplot(mct)

```

```
#####
```

Statistical test of relationship between MCT and ICE

```

mct_origin<-mct_df
colnames(mct_origin)
table(mct_origin$Sice_relatd)

mct_origin$Sice_type <- ifelse(mct_origin$assembly %in%
unique(ice_meta$assembly_id[ice_meta$Sice_complete=="Complete-ICE"]), "Complete ICE",
  ifelse(mct_origin$assembly %in%
unique(ice_meta$assembly_id), "vICE", "No ICE detected"))
table(mct_origin$Sice_type)
setdiff(str_replace(mct_origin$specie.y,"_", " "), ice_meta$taxonkit_specie)

```

```

ICE "Ureaplasma parvum" "Mycoplasmopsis californica" "Acholeplasma laidlawii"
mct_origin$assembly[mct_origin$ice_type=="Complete ICE"] %>% unique() ## 35 mct and
8 genomes
mct_origin$contig[mct_origin$ice_type=="Complete ICE" & mct_origin$ice_relatd=="yes"]
mct_origin$mct_label[mct_origin$ice_type=="Complete ICE" &
mct_origin$ice_relatd=="yes"] ## 35 mct events
test_df <- data.frame(assembly=unique(metadata$assembly_id[metadata$specie %in%
str_replace(ncbi_hgts_meta$specie.x,"_", " ")])
test_df$ice_type <- ifelse(test_df$assembly %in%
unique(ice_meta$assembly_id[ice_meta$is_complete=="Complete-ICE"]), "Complete ICE",
ifelse(test_df$assembly %in% unique(ice_meta$assembly_id), "vICE", "No
ICE detected"))
test_df$mct <- ifelse(test_df$assembly %in%
unique(mct_phrase$assembly), "MCT_exist", "MCT_not_detected")
chisq_df <- table(test_df$mct, test_df$ice_type)
chisq.test(chisq_df, correct = TRUE) #p<0.001577
fisher.test(chisq_df) #p 0.00007068

```

Chord diagram

```

mct_s_e <- data.frame(mct_label=unique(mct_origin$mct_label), start=0, end=0)
for (mct in unique(mct_origin$mct_label)) {
  mct_contig <- mct_phrase[mct_phrase$mct_label==mct,]
  mct_start_i = min(mct_contig[, "start"])
  mct_end_i = max(mct_contig[, "end"])
  mct_s_e[mct_s_e$mct_label==mct, "start"] = mct_start_i
  mct_s_e[mct_s_e$mct_label==mct, "end"] = mct_end_i
}
mct_s_e$mct_length = mct_s_e$end - mct_s_e$start
mct_s_e$assemblyid =
mct_phrase$assembly[match(mct_s_e$mct_label, mct_phrase$mct_label)]
ggplot(mct_s_e, aes(mct_length)) + geom_density()
mct_s_e$contig = str_remove(mct_s_e$mct_label, pattern = "_[^_]+$")
mct_s_e$specie <- mct_phrase$specie.x[match(mct_s_e$contig, mct_phrase$contig)]

```

620 mct_origin

```

mct_blast <- read.table(quote = "#", file =
"C:/Users/zilic/Desktop/Manuscript/Figure/Figure6.MCT/blast_200max_over5000.txt")
colnames(mct_blast) <- c("query_id", "subject_id", "identity", "alignment_length",
"mismatches", "gap_opens", "q_start", "q_end", "s_start", "s_end", "query_length",
"subject_length", "query_coverage_per_subject", "query_coverage_per_hsp", "evaluate",
"bit_score")

```

```
## filter
```

```
mct_blast <- mct_blast[mct_blast$alignment_length > 5000,]
```

```

mct_blast$contig <- str_remove(mct_blast$query_id,":.*")
mct_blast <- mct_blast[mct_blast$contig != mct_blast$subject_id,]
mct_blast$specie <- mct_phrase$specie.x[match(mct_blast$contig,mct_phrase$contig)]
mct_blast$specie <- str_replace(mct_blast$specie,"_"," ")
mct_blast$assembly_origin <- contigid_to_assemblyid(mct_blast$subject_id)
mct_blast_taxinfo <- get_organism_from_taxonkit(mct_blast$assembly_origin)
mct_blast$specie_origin <- mct_blast_taxinfo$taxonkit_specie
mct_blast_select <- mct_blast[mct_blast$specie != mct_blast$specie_origin,]
mct_blast_select <- mct_blast_select[!is.na(mct_blast_select$query_id),]
mct_blast_select_unique <- mct_blast_select %>% distinct(query_id, specie_origin, .keep_all
= TRUE)
mct_blast_select_unique <-
mct_blast_select_unique[mct_blast_select_unique$query_coverage_per_subject>=60,]

```

```

unique(mct_blast_select_unique$specie)
unique(mct_blast_select_unique$specie_origin)

```

##plot

```

library(circlize)
library(reshape2)
df_string <- mct_blast_select_unique
mctx_long = as.data.frame(table(df_string$specie,df_string$specie_origin))
colnames(mctx_long) <- c("to","from","value")
mctx = dcast(mctx_long,to~from,value.var = "value")
dim(mctx)
mat = as.matrix(mctx[,2:19])
rownames(mat) = paste0(mctx$to,"_to")
colnames(mat)
rownames(mat)
brewer.pal(9, "Set1")
brewer.pal(8, "Dark2")
"#1B9E77" "#D95F02" "#7570B3" "#E7298A" "#66A61E" "#E6AB02" "#A6761D"
"#666666"
"#E41A1C" "#377EB8" "#4DAF4A" "#984EA3" "#FF7F00" "#FFFF33" "#A65628"
"#F781BF" "#999999"
col <- c('Acholeplasma laidlawii_to`="#1B9E77" ,
`Mesomycoplasma hyopneumoniae_to`="#D95F02",
`Mesomycoplasma hyorhinitis_to`= "#7570B3",
`Mycoplasma arginini_to`= "#E7298A" ,
`Mycoplasma fermentans_to`=#33538E',
`Ureaplasma parvum_to`= "#E6AB02",
`Ureaplasma urealyticum_to` ="#A65628",
`Spiroplasma citri_to`="#FFFF33",
`Spiroplasma melliferum_to`= "#E41A1C" ,
`Spiroplasma poulsonii_to`="#66A61E",

```

```

`Mesomycoplasma conjunctivae` = 'grey50',
`Mycoplasma enhydrae` = 'grey50',
`Mycoplasma sp.` = 'grey50',
`Mycoplasma struthionis` = 'grey50',
`Spiroplasma citri` = 'grey50',
`Spiroplasma endosymbiont of Phyllotreta cruciferae` = 'grey50',
`Spiroplasma melliferum` = 'grey50',
`Spiroplasma sp. ChiS` = 'grey50',
`Spiroplasma sp. hyd1` = 'grey50',
`Spiroplasma sp. NBRC 100390` = 'grey50',
`Spiroplasma sp. TU-14` = 'grey50',"grey50")

```

```

circos.clear()

```

```

chordDiagram(mat, grid.col = col,
  transparency = 0.2,
  link.lwd = 1.8,
  link.lty = 1,
  link.border = "black",
  grid.border = 'black',
  annotationTrack = "grid")

```

```

circos.track(track.index = 1, panel.fun = function(x, y) {
  circos.text(CELL_META$xcenter, CELL_META$ylim[1], CELL_META$sector.index,
    facing = "clockwise", niceFacing = TRUE, adj = c(-0.2, 0.5))
}, bg.border = NA)

```

```

chordDiagram(mat, grid.col = col,
  order =c( "Spiroplasma citri_to",
    "Spiroplasma melliferum_to",
    "Spiroplasma poulsonii_to",
    "Mycoplasma mopsis arginini_to",
    "Mycoplasma mopsis fermentans_to", colnames(mat)),
  transparency = 0.2,
  link.lwd = 1.8,
  link.lty = 1,
  link.border = "black",
  grid.border = 'black',
  annotationTrack = "grid")

```

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